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SOPs for sampling in matrices shared within the Consortium

WP1 (Sampling strategy) developed Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for sampling within the complex matrices which will be collected in the same WP1 and used for subsequent WPs. Collected matrices will span the whole food chain, from faeces and intestines of the definitive carnivore hosts to vegetables for human consumption, and cysts in the intermediate livestock hosts.

SOPs were generated for:

- **COLLECTION OF *ECHINOCOCCUS GRANULOSUS SENSU LATO* CYSTS FROM NATURALLY INFECTED SHEEP AND PIGS** (pag.3)
- **COLLECTION OF FAECAL SAMPLES FROM DOGS FOR THE MOLECULAR IDENTIFICATION OF *ECHINOCOCCUS* spp.** (pag.6)
- **MATRICES COLLECTION FROM EXPERIMENTAL MICE AND RED FOXES INFECTIONS** (pag.7)
- **VALIDATION OF SEGMENTAL SEDIMENTATION AND COUNTING TECHNIQUE (SSCT) FOR DIAGNOSTIC OF *ECHINOCOCCUS MULTILOCULARIS* IN FOX** (pag.10)
- **NEW MICROSATELLITES MARKERS FOR *ECHINOCOCCUS GRANULOSUS SENSU STRICTO* FOR SOURCE ATTRIBUTION** (pag.13)
- **SAMPLING OF VEGETABLES FOR HUMAN CONSUMPTION AND THEIR PROCESSING FOR THE MOLECULAR IDENTIFICATION OF *ECHINOCOCCUS* SPP. AND *TAENIA* SPP. EGGS** (pag.14)
- **QUESTIONNAIRE FOR SAMPLING DOGS** (pag.17)

- **COLLECTION OF *ECHINOCOCCUS GRANULOSUS SENSU LATO* CYSTS FROM NATURALLY INFECTED SHEEP AND PIGS**

1. SCOPE

This Standard Operating Procedure provides instructions to collect *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* (*s.l.*) cysts-derived material from naturally infected sheep and pigs for molecular analyses in the framework of MEME project, One Health European Joint Programme.

2. INTRODUCTION

Cystic echinococcosis (CE) is zoonotic diseases caused by larval stages of *Echinococcus granulosus s.l.* The life cycle of this parasite involves mainly domestic but also wild ungulates as intermediate hosts. Canids, mainly dogs, play a role of definitive hosts harbouring adult worms in their small intestine. Humans play the role of dead-end intermediate host (WHO/OIE 2000). CE is a life-threatening parasitic zoonosis with substantial public health impact worldwide (Budke et al., 2017). The material collected from cysts may be used for molecular study for the improvement and validation of diagnostic tests.

3. REFERENCES

WHO/OIE Manual on Echinococcosis in Humans and Animals: a Public Health Problem of Global Concern (ed. Eckert, J., Gemmell, M. A., Meslin, F.-X. & Pawloski, Z. S.) pp. 265. World Organization for Animal Health, Paris, France, 2001. ISBN 92-9044-522-X. &8364;40.
Budke, et al. Cystic and alveolar echinococcosis: Successes and continuing challenges. PLoS Negl Trop Dis. 2017 Apr 20;11(4):e000547.

4. EQUIPMENT

- Scissors, tweezers, knife (scalpel);
- Plastic tightly closed wide-mouth containers (minimum 150 mL) or tightly closed plastic bags (that can be stored at -20°C);
- Gloves;
- Waterproof marker (for marking containers);
- Freezer (-20°C);
- Centrifuge tubes (15 mL, 1.5mL);
- Centrifuge (minimum 2000xg);
- Plastic Pasteur pipettes;
- Petri dishes;
- Microscope (magnification minimum 40x).

5. REAGENTS

Not applicable

6. PROCEDURE

a) In slaughterhouse

- a. during examination of carcasses identify visually CE cysts in organs (liver, lungs) according to typical morphological characteristics (Fig. 1). Typically, *E. granulosus s.l.* produces a single-chambered unilocular whitish cyst which is growing by concentric enlargement. Occasionally, cysts may abut and coalesce, forming groups or clusters of small cysts of different size (WHO/OIE 2000).
- b. Use knife, scalpel or scissors to collect, without damaging, the cyst. Cut the Pericyst (host tissue surrounding the cyst) and put the sample in the plastic container or bag;
- c. Mark the container to be identifiable;
- d. Sample must be frozen at -20°C during 48 hours to avoid DNA degeneration before sending to the laboratory.

Fig. 1. *Echinococcus granulosus s.l.* cysts.

b) In laboratory

- a. Sample must be stored at -20°C in the laboratory before analysis;
- b. Preparation of sample for molecular identification (Fig. 2)
 - i. Cut the external wall of the cyst and isolate the inner bladder (germinal layer). Avoid cross contamination using always sterile tools for individual samples;
 - ii. Put the germinal layer in the petri dish and cut it into small pieces;
 - iii. Aspirate the cyst fluid by pipette and put it in a centrifuge tube;
 - iv. Centrifuge the cyst fluid at $2000\times g$ and check the drop of the sediment under the microscope (magnification at least $\times 40$) to detect protoscoleces;
 - v. Put aliquots of the protoscoleces sediment in Eppendorf tubes (1.5 or 2.0 mL). If there are no protoscoleces put aliquots of the pellet in Eppendorf tubes;
 - vi. Additionally cut the wall of inner bladder (with germinal layer) and put them into Eppendorf (1.5 or 2.0 mL) tubes;
 - vii. Samples must be stored at -20°C in the before further molecular analysis.

Fig. 2. *Echinococcus granulosus s.l.* cysts preparation in laboratory

7. SAFETY MEASURES

The operator should wear individual protection devices during the test performance. For general safety measures, refer to the guidelines of CDC (http://www.who.int/ihr/publications/bioriskmanagement_1/en/).

- **COLLECTION OF FAECAL SAMPLES FROM DOGS FOR THE MOLECULAR IDENTIFICATION OF ECHINOCOCCUS spp.**

8. SCOPE

This Standard Operating Procedure provides instructions to collect samples of dog faeces for molecular epidemiological study on *Echinococcus* spp. in the framework of MEME project, One Health European Joint Programme.

9. INTRODUCTION

Cystic and alveolar echinococcosis (CE and AE) are zoonotic diseases caused by larval stages of *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* (*s.l.*) and *Echinococcus multilocularis*, respectively. The life cycle of these parasites involves mainly small rodents for *E. multilocularis* or domestic and wild ungulates for *E. granulosus s.l.* as intermediate hosts. Canids, mainly foxes (*E. multilocularis*) or dogs (*E. multilocularis* and *E. granulosus s.l.*) play a role of definitive hosts harbouring adult worms in their small intestine. Humans play the role of dead-end intermediate host (WHO/OIE 2000). AE and CE are life-threatening parasitic zoonosis with substantial public health impact worldwide (Budke et al., 2017).

Dog faeces infected with parasite eggs are important source of infection for humans. Even low prevalence of *Echinococcus* spp. may cause significant risk of infection. That is why the monitoring of the epidemiological situation in dogs is important from a public health prospective.

Copro-PCR is one of the most effective and commonly used *ante mortem* method for the detection of specific *Echinococcus* DNA in definitive hosts (EFSA 2015).

10. REFERENCES

WHO/OIE Manual on Echinococcosis in Humans and Animals: a Public Health Problem of Global Concern (ed. Eckert, J., Gemmell, M. A., Meslin, F.-X. & Pawloski, Z. S.) pp. 265. World Organization for Animal Health, Paris, France, 2001. ISBN 92-9044-522-X. &8364;40.

Budke, et al. Cystic and alveolar echinococcosis: Successes and continuing challenges. PLoS Negl Trop Dis. 2017 Apr 20;11(4):e000547.

EFSA. Panel on Animal Health and Welfare 2015. Scientific opinion on Echinococcus multilocularis infection in animals. EFSA Journal 2015, 13, 4373, doi:doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2015.4373.

Umhang, G.; Raton, V.; Comte, S.; Hormaz, V.; Boucher, J.M.; Combes, B.; Boue, F. Echinococcus multilocularis in dogs from two French endemic areas: No evidence of infection but hazardous deworming practices. Vet Parasitol 2012, 188, 301–305, doi:10.1016/j.vetpar.2012.03.024.

Irie, T.; Yamada, K.; Morishima, Y.; Yagi, K. High probability of pet dogs encountering the sylvatic cycle of Echinococcus multilocularis in a rural area in Hokkaido, Japan. Journal of Veterinary Medical Science 2019, 81, 1606-1608, doi:10.1292/jvms.19-0307.

11. EQUIPMENT

- Wooden or plastic spatulas;
- Plastic tightly closed container for faeces (that can be stored at -80°C);
- Gloves;
- Waterproof marker (for marking containers with the individual codes);
- Freezers (-20°C and -80°C).

12. REAGENTS

Not applicabe.

13. PROCEDURE

- c) Faecal sample has to be collect as fresh as possible - possibly the same day of defecation;
- d) Faecal samples should be associated to individual and known dog (use the questionnaire to provide this information);
- e) Collect faeces with the use of spatula (weight of the sample of around 3-5 g - the size of the walnut) and transfer faeces into the container (plastic, tightly closed);
- f) Mark the container with a code (the same as reported in the questionnaire);

- g) Questionnaire connected with the sample must be filled by dog owner or the person collecting the sample;
- h) Sample must be frozen at -20°C during 48 hours to avoid DNA degeneration before sending to the laboratory;
- i) Sample must be stored at -20°C in the laboratory before analysis;
- j) For safety reasons, before handling the sample for lab analysis it should be stored at -80°C for at least 7 days to inactivate potentially present *Echinococcus* eggs.

14. SAFETY MEASURES

The operator should wear individual protection devices during the test performance. For general safety measures, refer to the guidelines of CDC (http://www.who.int/ihr/publications/bioriskmanagement_1/en/).

• MATRICES COLLECTION FROM EXPERIMENTAL MICE AND RED FOXES INFECTIONS

15. SCOPE

This Standard Operating Procedure provides instructions to produce reference material from experimental infections by *Echinococcus multilocularis* in mice and in red foxes as well as infection by *Echinococcus granulosus sensu stricto* in red foxes in the framework of MEME project, One Health European Joint Programme.

16. INTRODUCTION

Cystic and alveolar echinococcosis (CE and AE) are zoonoses involving canids as definitive hosts and a broad spectrum of ungulate species as intermediate hosts. Humans are considered as dead-end hosts for the larval stage of these parasites. AE and CE are important diseases of human interest with a global distribution (Thompson, 2017) caused by infection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* (Em) and *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* (Eg), respectively. The definitive hosts (mainly red fox for Em and dog for Eg) shed eggs in the environment by faeces. The oral ingestion of these eggs may result in human infections.

A reference material is necessary to allow a rigorous comparison and assessment of the performances of newly developed parasitological and molecular methods against the existing techniques targeting the definitive and intermediate hosts of Em and Eg. Controlled production of parasitic material in intermediate host is also necessary for experimental infection of definitive host and vice versa.

17. REFERENCE

Eckert J, Thompson R. C. A. (2017). Chapter One: Historical Aspects of Echinococcosis, *Advances in Parasitology* (95):1-64.

18. AUTHORIZATION FOR ANIMAL EXPERIMENTATION

Animal experimentation facilities necessity specific authorizations:

=> Ethical authorization for animal testing delivered by local authorities, relating to the protection of animals used for scientific purposes (for Anses, Decree n ° 2013-118 dated 1 February 2013)

=> Specific authorization for red foxes use because they are wild animals: Authorizations, structures and specific technical expertise to capture and keep wild animals, setting the general operating rules for animal breeding facilities for non-domestic animals (for Anses, Order of April 18, 2016 D54-431-1)

=> Ethical authorizations corresponding to the protocol use for experimental infection of carnivores by Em from larval stage produce in mice to worm in foxes (for Anses, 16-073 N° APAFiS: 2016091313348095 notice number: 11/10/16-3)

19. EQUIPMENT

• Mice infection

- Mice (BalbC or Swiss)
- The plastic box Foxes
- Mice food
- Animal enriching (Hut, Tub.)
- Water feeder
- Microscope
- Scissors
- Forceps
- Stainless Colander
- Falcon tubes 50 ml
- Syringe / Needle 30G
- Freezers (-20°C and -80°C)

• Red foxes infection

- Red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*)
- Foxes cages
- Specific faeces collect system
- Carnivore food
- Water feeder
- Esophageal tracheal airway/ Combitude
- Gas anaesthesia apparatus
- Plastic tightly closed container for faeces
- Syringe
- Scissors
- Forceps
- Plastic bag
- Freezers (-80°C)

20. PRODUCTION OF LARVAL STAGE

- Obtaining fresh living larval mass from field or laboratory strain
- Crushing cysts with scissors in PBS
- Strainer filtration (removal of tissue structures)
- Washing with PBS
- Decanting pellet
- Remove the supernatant
- Repeat washing until obtaining a clear supernatant
- Suspending pellet containing protoscoleces in PBS
- Collect solution with 1 mL syringe with 30G needle
- Intraperitoneal injection in mice (500 - 1000µl)
- Wait 4 to 6 months for the larval stage to development.

⇒ Larval stage collection

- l) Mouse euthanasia
- m) Autopsy of mice
- n) Larval mass / protoscoleces isolation

⇒ use for new production of the larval stage in mice come back to a)

⇒ use for fox infection;

21. PRODUCTION OF ADULT WORMS AND EGGS

- a) Fox gas anesthesia
- b) Esophageal Intubation
- c) Infection with Em or Eg protoscoleces preparation by injection via the Esophageal tracheal airway tub directly in the stomach.
- d) Animal wake-up control
- e) Return in a cage suitable for feces collection (with drawers) in control area (P2+)
- f) Daily collection of feces in plastic boxes
- g) Conservation a +4°C, -20°C or -80°C according to downstream application

⇒ **Option 1:** without fox euthanasia, until 90 dpi

- h) Deworming of infected fox with a treatment containing praziquantel
- i) Twice deworming 2 days later for safety
- j) Return of the fox to a non-infected area

⇒ **Option 2:** with final euthanasia of the fox, from 25 to 90 dpi

- k) Euthanasia according to animal welfare
- l) Necropsy
- m) Collection of the intestine in a plastic bag
- n) Freezing a -80°C

22. SAFETY MEASURES

The operator should wear individual protection devices during the test performance. For general safety measures, refer to the guidelines of CDC (http://www.who.int/ihr/publications/bioriskmanagement_1/en/).

- **VALIDATION OF SEGMENTAL SEDIMENTATION AND COUNTING TECHNIQUE (SSCT) FOR DIAGNOSTIC OF ECHINOCOCCUS MULTILOCULARIS IN FOX**

23. SCOPE

This Standard Operating Procedure provides instructions on Segmental Sedimentation and Counting Technique (SSCT) for the identification of the adult worms of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in the intestines of foxes in the framework of MEME project, One Health European Joint Programme.

24. INTRODUCTION

Alveolar echinococcosis (AE) is a zoonotic parasitic disease involving canids as definitive host (mainly fox) for the adult worm stage and a broad spectrum of small rodent species as intermediate hosts for the larval stage. Humans are considered as dead-end hosts for the larval stage of this parasite. AE is considered as a severe disease of human interest with a northern hemisphere distribution caused by infection of the tapeworm *E. multilocularis* (Em). The infected definitive hosts harbour worms in their intestines, which are shedding eggs in the environment by faeces. The oral ingestion of these eggs may result in human infections.

The diagnosis of Em infection in the definitive host is important for epidemiological studies to estimate presence and prevalence of the parasite in the studied areas. Difficulties in the detection of the adult parasite in definitive hosts mainly derive from the irregular shedding of Em eggs and the inability to distinguish them morphologically from those of *Taenia* spp. Since the available diagnostic methods differ among laboratories both methodologically and in their performances, there is a need to validate and harmonize the detection methods. The SSCT was developed using the SCT (Sedimentation and counting technique) which is considered the reference method for diagnostic of Em infections in foxes by WHO (2001). The SSCT method is based on the principle of preferential distribution of Em worms in the posterior part of the small intestine in order to achieve a significant saving of analysis time but while maintaining a very high sensitivity.

25. REFERENCES

Umhang, G., Woronoff-Rhen, N., Combes, B., & Boué, F. (2011). Segmental sedimentation and counting technique (SSCT): An adaptable method for qualitative diagnosis of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in fox intestines. *Experimental Parasitology*, 128 (1), 57-60.

WHO/OIE Manual on Echinococcosis in Humans and Animals: a Public Health Problem of Global Concern (2001). Edited by J. Eckert, M.A. Gemmell, F.X. Meslin and Z.S. Pawlowski.

26. SAMPLING

The whole intestine (small and large intestine) need to be sampled from fox originated from Em endemic areas. A decontamination period at -80°C during at least four days is required in order to prevent any risk of Em infection. The samples can be stored at -20°C before and/or after this decontamination step.

27. EQUIPMENT

- Plastic tray (to place the intestines);
- Dissecting scissors;
- Pliers;
- Four plastic bottles of 250 ML each;
- Waste bin for biological waste;
- 0.5 to 1 mm mesh filter with additional threads;
- Four funnels
- Four Erlenmeyers wide collar 100 ML;
- 5.9. Automatic pipette and plastic pipette 50 ml;
- 5.10. 1 L plastic spout containing a disinfectant detergent to receive the supernatant;
- 5.11. Four measuring cylinders 50 ML;
- 5.12. Binocular magnifying glass;
- 5.13. Grid reading tank (or Petri dish).

28. REAGENTS

- Distilled water or physiological solution.

29. PROCEDURE

Starting material consists of intestines (small and large part) stored frozen and thawed at 4°C the night before or at room temperature a few hours before for the SSCT analysis. All steps are performed at room temperature as follows:

- **Scrapping**

- The intestine is rolled out and arranged in a zigzag pattern to form 5 segments: four equal segment from small intestines when the last segment consists of the large intestine exclusively;
- The segment are numbered from S1 to S5 from the anterior to the posterior part;
- The intestine is cut off at the end of each segment using scissor and the large intestine segment (S5) is eliminated;
- The four segments are then opened along their entire length, worm clusters (*Taenia* sp., roundworms) and other debris that would prevent filtration are removed using pliers;
- Each segment is placed in an identified sealed (S1 to S4) plastic bottle containing 100ml of distilled water or physiological solution;
- The bottles are shaken vigorously during two minutes;

- For each segment, the intestinal mucosa is scraped between two fingers above the vial, along its entire length, in one direction and then in the other, in order to loosen the fixed parasites and the intestine fragment is thrown into the waste bin.

- **Filtration**

- The contents of each bottle is then filtered through a 0.5 to 1 mm mesh filter above a 100 ml wide neck Erlenmeyer with funnel;
- After sedimentation of about one hour, the supernatant is eliminated in each of the Erlenmeyer using an automatic pipette and thrown into a plastic Becher containing a disinfectant detergent;
- For each segment, the pellet is homogenized and transferred to a 50 ml measuring cylinder.

- **Observation**

The four segments must be observed by scanning the grid reading tank under binocular magnifier (x100).

- a) A few milliliters of intestinal contents are deposited in a grid reading tank and dilute directly by adding distilled water;
- b) After observation, the contents are disposed in a plastic Becher containing a disinfectant detergent, and the tank is rinsed with distilled water to be reuse.

- **Interpretation of the results**

Parasite in the intestinal content

E. multilocularis worm

An individual result for all of the four segments (S1 to S4) for each animal must be obtained. The estimation of the worm burden for each segment will be obtained by the observation of 20% of the volume of the intestinal content of a segment if at least one *E. multilocularis* worm was observed in the volume corresponding to the 20%. When any worm was observed in the 20% portion from the segment, all the volume of the segment must be observed even if one worm was observed after.

The estimation of the worm burden will be very important to estimate the distribution of the worms in the intestine and will be finally divided in four categories: 1-10, 11-100, 101-1000, >1000 worms.

30. SAFETY MEASURES

The operator should wear individual protection devices during the test performance. For general safety measures, refer to WHO/OIE Manual on Echinococcosis in Humans and Animals: a Public Health Problem of Global Concern (2001)

(<https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/42427>).

- **NEW MICROSATELLITES MARKERS FOR ECHINOCOCCUS GRANULOSUS SENSU STRICTO FOR SOURCE ATTRIBUTION**

31. SCOPE

This Standard Operating Procedure provides instructions for the genotyping using new microsatellites markers for *E. granulosus sensu stricto* (Eg ss) in order to identify source attribution in the framework of MEME project, One Health European Joint Programme.

32. INTRODUCTION

Cystic echinococcosis (CE) is a zoonotic disease involving canids as definitive hosts and a broad spectrum of livestock species as intermediate hosts. Humans are considered dead-end hosts for the larval stage of this parasite. CE is an important disease of human interest with a global distribution (Thompson, Deplazes, Lymbery 2017) caused by infection of *Echinococcus granulosus* (Eg) *sensu lato*. The infected definitive hosts (mainly dog) are shedding eggs in the environment by faeces. The oral ingestion of these eggs may result in human infections. Source attribution for human infections is generally unknown, but hand-to-mouth and the food-waterborne borne transmissions may have a pivotal role. As eggs are inactivated by heat (i.e. cooking), the consumption of fresh vegetables contaminated with viable eggs could lead to human infections.

Today very scanty data are available on the degree of such contamination. Recent sequencing of the full genome of Eg ss opens possibility to screen for microsatellite sequences in order to be able to build up a robust, fast and reliable panel of microsatellites markers with a high discriminatory power relevant to perform source attribution.

33. REFERENCES

- M'rad, S.; Oudni-M'rad, M.; Bastid, V.; Bournez, L.; Mosbahi, S.; Nouri, A.; Babba, H.; Grenouillet, F.; Boué, F.; Umhang, G. Microsatellite Investigations of Multiple *Echinococcus granulosus* Sensu Stricto Cysts in Single Hosts Reveal Different Patterns of Infection Events between Livestock and Humans. *Pathogens* 2020, 9, 444.
- Tsai IJ et al (2013) The genomes of four tapeworm species reveal adaptations to parasitism. *Nature* 496(7443):57–63.
- Umhang, G.; Grenouillet, F.; Bastid, V.; M'rad, S.; Valot, B.; Oudni-M'rad, M.; Babba, H.; Boué, F. Investigating the genetic diversity of *Echinococcus granulosus sensu stricto* with new microsatellites. *Parasitol. Res.* 2018, 117, 2743–2755.

34. SAMPLING

A collection of human/animal CE samples from different geographical and host origins will be analysed using the selected microsatellites in order to evaluate them before to use a larger panel of samples to validate the final panel of microsatellites markers.

35. EQUIPMENT

- Thermocycler;
- Sequencing machine;

36. PROCEDURE

All steps are performed at room temperature in dedicated molecular biology rooms as follows:

- **Screening for and selection of microsatellite repeats**
 - a) The genome sequences of *E. granulosus* (v2 03232012) were downloaded from the Sanger Institute website (Tsai et al. 2013);
 - b) Screening for microsatellites was performed using the Tandem Repeats Finder software (<https://tandem.bu.edu/trf/trf.html>) (Benson 1999);
 - c) Among proposed repeated patterns, only microsatellites showing at least ten repeated units and showing unit length comprised between 3 and 10 were selected.

- **Selection of microsatellite repeats**

- a) For the best candidates, PCR primer pairs were designed using Primer 3 software (Rozen and Skaletsky 2000);
- b) PCR was carried out in a final volume of 25 µl using the Qiagen multiplex PCR Master Mix and primers at a final concentration of 0.2 µM each;
- c) The amplification reaction was performed in a thermal cycler, under the following conditions: a pre-amplification step of 95 °C for 15 min, followed by 30 cycles with a denaturing step at 94 °C for 30 s, annealing at 60 °C for 90 s, and extension at 72 °C for 1 min, with a final elongation at 60 °C for 45 min;
- d) If successful PCR amplifications were observed after migration on agarose gel electrophoresis, PCR was repeated using a fluorescent forward primer;
- e) Capillary electrophoresis of PCR products was performed on a sequencer machine;
- f) The size and height of each peak were determined with the use of GeneMapper 4.1.

- **Characterization of the microsatellites**

- a) The repeatability was assessed by three amplifications of each microsatellite for three different Eg ss DNAs, followed by three capillary electrophoresis migrations for each PCR product;
- b) The reproducibility was assessed by having all the analyses repeated by a second operator;
- c) The detection limit of the microsatellites was estimated using two DNA samples extracted from protoscoleces of Eg ss cysts with a dilution range from 1 ng to 1 fg;
- d) The specificity of amplification was tested using DNAs from the larval stage of different *Taenia* sp., *Echinococcus* sp.;
- e) Sequencing was performed from PCR products of CE samples to confirm the presence of the microsatellite motif. The sequences obtained were compared with those from the genome available from the Sanger Institute to identify potential sequence variations;
- f) The discriminatory power was evaluated by calculating Simpson's Diversity Index (Hunter and Gaston 1988) with the whole panel of Eg ss DNA samples in order to establish comparisons with other techniques (e.g. mitochondrial sequencing).

- **Application of the microsatellite panel in an epidemiological context of source attribution**

To be defined according to the panel of CE DNA samples that will be available.

37. SAFETY MEASURES

The operator should wear individual protection devices during the test performance. For general safety measures, refer to the guidelines of CDC (http://www.who.int/ihr/publications/bioriskmanagement_1/en/).

- **SAMPLING OF VEGETABLES FOR HUMAN CONSUMPTION AND THEIR PROCESSING FOR THE MOLECULAR IDENTIFICATION OF ECHINOCOCCUS SPP. AND TAENIA SPP. EGGS**

38. SCOPE

This Standard Operating Procedure provides instructions for the collection of fresh lettuce and its processing using a sequential sieving for the molecular identification of *Echinococcus* spp. and *Taenia* spp. eggs in the framework of MEME project, One Health European Joint Programme.

39. INTRODUCTION

Cystic and alveolar echinococcosis (CE and AE) are zoonoses involving canids as definitive hosts and a broad spectrum of ungulate species or rodents as intermediate hosts. Humans are considered dead-end hosts for the larval stage of these parasites. AE and CE are important diseases of human interest with a global distribution (Thompson, Deplazes, Lymbery, 2017) caused by infection with *Echinococcus multilocularis* (Em) and *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* (Eg), respectively. The infected definitive hosts (mainly red fox for Em and dog for Eg) are shedding eggs in the environment by faeces. The oral ingestion of these eggs may result in human infections. Source attribution for human infections is generally unknown, but hand-to-mouth and the food-waterborne borne transmissions may have a pivotal role. As eggs are inactivated by heat (i.e. cooking), the consumption of fresh vegetables contaminated with viable eggs could lead to human infections.

Very scanty data are currently available on the degree of such contaminations (Tamarozzi et al., 2020). Development of a robust and reliable methods coupling with the concentration of the eggs and sensitive

/ specific molecular tools for species identification are required to estimate the contamination of fresh vegetables by these parasites. The sequential sieving method recently developed by Guggisberg et al. (2020) will be used with lettuce collected from vegetable markets and kitchen gardens.

40. REFERENCES

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41. SAMPLING

The lettuce sampled should be originated from known *E. multilocularis* and/or *E. granulosus sensu lato* endemic areas, ideally where high prevalence in animal hosts are reported. Only lettuce originated from known geographical areas need to be included. Additionally, sampling should be conducted in private kitchen garden, vegetable market or in a lesser extent supermarkets, where lettuce was cultivated in open land potentially accessible to canids (excluding closed greenhouse cultivation).

Lettuce collected from the same field of cultivation will be pooled during the analysis at the rate of two lettuces for private kitchen gardens and four lettuces for commercial producer considering the larger surface of cultivation used.

One lettuce sample consists of around 300 g of leaves or the complete lettuce if the total weight is inferior to 300 g.

42. EQUIPMENT

- Two small plastic bottles cut in half with lids perforated;
- One big plastic bottle cut in half with lid perforated;
- One base to support the three bottles funnel;
- Nylon filters of different mesh size (21 µm, 40 µm and 105 µm);
- Three Single-use plastic pipettes;
- One plastic sample bag;
- Scissors;
- One 50 mL Falcon tubes;
- One 2 mL microtube;
- Centrifuge;
- One clamp;
- Analytical balance.

43. REAGENTS

- Solution of 0.2% Tween 20.

44. PROCEDURE

Starting material consists of lettuce freshly collected or conserved at +4°C for no more than 3 days. All steps are performed at room temperature as follows:

- **Preparation of the equipment and of the samples**

- Put the three filters on the perforated lids and screw it on the funnel bottles (starting from the top: 105 μ m, 40 μ m and 21 μ m);
- Annotate the funnel bottles with the size of the filter mesh;
- Place the funnel bottles on the base with the 105 μ m mesh filter on the highest place, then the 40 μ m and finally the 20 μ m mesh filter;
- Place the bottom parts of the big bottle for the collection of the flow-through;
- Put 300 g of lettuce leaves, giving priority to those outer leaves whose appearance would not require removal from the consumer, in a sample plastic bag;
- Add 500 mL of 0.2% Tween 20 in the sample plastic bag;
- Close the bag and shake it vigorously for more than 30 sec while stirring to detach as much residue as possible from the leaves.

- **Sequential sieving**

- Using a pair of scissors, cut an angle at the bottom of the bag to create an opening for pouring the contents to be filtered;
- Pour the solution into the upper bottle (105 μ m mesh size) and let it will flow through the following bottles;
- Squeeze the bag well so that the maximum amount of solution is recovered;
- Remove the lettuce and then, using a pipette containing 0.02% Tween 20 to rinse the bag, then filter the rinsing liquid;
- Use a single-use pipette in each of the bottle to facilitate the flow;
- Once the solution has been fully filtered, starting from the top use the single-use pipette to rinse the bottles with the 0.2% Tween 20 solution.

- **Collection of the substrate from the 20 μ m filter**

- Unscrew the lid and use clamp to retrieve the 20 μ m filter;
- Hold the filter with the forceps in the 50 mL Falcon tube and use the 0.2% Tween 20 pipette to rinse the filter;
- Centrifuge the 50 mL Falcon tube for 5 min at 1000 g;
- Discard the supernatant;
- Collect the pellet in a 2 mL microtube and store at +4°C until the DNA extraction.

- **Detection by molecular biology**

DNA extraction is realized using Blood & Tissue kit (Qiagen) with an additional overnight lysis step. The detection of *E. multilocularis* is performed by a real-time PCR assay as previously described (Knapp et al., 2016) when classical PCR followed by sequencing is used to identify *Taenia* sp. (Trachsel et al., 2007).

45. SAFETY MEASURES

The operator should wear individual protection devices during the test performance. For general safety measures, refer to the guidelines of CDC (http://www.who.int/ihr/publications/bioriskmanagement_1/en/).

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR SAMPLING DOGS

Sample ID (<i>fill by owner/collector</i>) (the same ID has to be on the sample); 	Collection date: yyyy/mm/dd	Lab code (<i>fill in laboratory</i>):
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Data about the owner:

Owner name:	Owner surname
Address:	Zip code, city:.....

Data about the dog:

Dog name:	Breed:	Sex: <input type="checkbox"/> F <input type="checkbox"/> M	Age (y):
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Place of living: <input type="checkbox"/> Urban <input type="checkbox"/> peri-urban (< 5km from a city/town) <input type="checkbox"/> Rural (>5km from a city/town)
--

About dog's activities: (multiple answers can be selected)

Activity sites:	Never	at least once per year	at least once per month	at least once per week	at least once per day
Backyard	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Public park	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Fields	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Forest	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Other	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Type of activity:				
<input type="checkbox"/> Urban walks	<input type="checkbox"/> Rural walks	<input type="checkbox"/> Hunting	<input type="checkbox"/> Watch-dog	<input type="checkbox"/> Other.....
<input type="checkbox"/> <i>only on a leash</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> <i>only on a leash</i>			

Has the dog ever eaten rodents? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Not to my knowledge
--

Deworming

Deworming frequency:	Never	less than once a year	once a year	twice a year	once every 3 months	once a month
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Last deworming (date)			Name of anthelmintic drug:			

About dog feeding (multiple answers can be selected)

<input type="checkbox"/> Raw meat	<input type="checkbox"/> commercial food	<input type="checkbox"/> food prepared in-house	<input type="checkbox"/> access to slaughter waste	<input type="checkbox"/> hunting game
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Other

If the dog lives on a farm, there are: <input type="checkbox"/> pigs, <input type="checkbox"/> sheep, <input type="checkbox"/> cattle, <input type="checkbox"/> other....., <input type="checkbox"/> No farm animals
Home slaughtering: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, <input type="checkbox"/> No

Declaration of the owner:

I agree to the use of the sample material and the questionnaire answers for scientific purposes. In this case all information will be made anonymous. I agree that results of the research may be used for scientific study and publication.

Date and signature: _____